

The figure of Ki Hajar Dewantara and Its Relevance in the Challenges of 21st Century Education

Anita Chandra Dewi^{1*}, Nur Annisa Islamiyah SR², Adela³, Nurul Magfirah⁴,
Julinda Yunita Sogen⁵, Ahmad Rifki⁶
Agricultural Technology Education, Makassar State University
Corresponding Author: Anita Chandra Dewi anitacandradewi@unm.ac.id

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords: Ki Hajar Dewantara, Relevance, Challenges, 21st Century Education

Received : 12, September

Revised : 15, October

Accepted: 28, November

©2023 Dewi, SR, Adela, Magfirah, Sogen, Rifki: This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

ABSTRACT

In the history of Indonesian education, the name Ki Hajar Dewantara occupies an honorable position as the father of national education. The 21st century, known as the era of digitalization, brings a number of new challenges to the world of education. In the midst of the rapid flow of information, there are concerns about how education can shape students' strong character, integrity and responsibility Ki Hajar Dewantara's collection of works is a source of primary and secondary data. Secondary data sources consist of writings, other works, or previous research about Ki Hajar Dewantara. This research shows that one of the famous educational figures in Indonesia, Ki Hajar Dewantara, who is known as a pioneer of national education, is highly respected. Ki Hajar Dewantara's thoughts such as holistic thinking, education rooted in educational culture, and independence in education remain relevant and provide valuable guidance in the era of globalization and digitalization.

INTRODUCTION

In the history of Indonesian education, the name Ki Hajar Dewantara occupies an honorable position as the father of national education. His educational philosophy that underlies the Indonesian education system, particularly the principle of "Tut Wuri Handayani", gives direction to how education is ideally implemented. In an era marked by rapid technological change, globalization, and other multidimensional challenges, the question of the relevance of Ki Hajar Dewantara's ideas in the 21st century is an interesting topic to be examined.

The 21st century, known as the era of digitalization, brings a number of new challenges in the world of education. The teaching and learning process that used to be centered on face-to-face interaction, is now starting to shift with the existence of digital learning methods. Technology, which facilitates access to information and communication, also brings its own challenges in terms of information quality, integrity, and relevance. In this context, how can the principles of Ki Hajar Dewantara be adopted to ensure quality education is still realized?

Character education is one aspect that gets special attention in this century. In the midst of such a heavy flow of information, there are concerns about how education can shape the character of students who are strong, integrity, and responsible. Ki Hajar Dewantara always emphasizes the importance of emotional, spiritual, and intellectual education. How can this holistic approach be implemented in today's digital age? Other issues such as inclusivity, gender equality, and sustainability are also significant challenges in 21st century education. As a thinker who places education as a tool to advance the nation and society, Ki Hajar Dewantara's thoughts can provide valuable insights into how education can be a solution to these issues. In particular, how education can be used as an instrument to build a more inclusive, equitable, and sustainable society.

As changes and challenges emerge, there is an urgent need for introspection and deep reflection on our current education system. Re-exploring Ki Hajar Dewantara's thinking and integrating it with the modern context can provide valuable guidance for education practitioners, policy makers, and other stakeholders in creating education that is adaptive, relevant, and has a positive impact on future generations.

Along with this urgency, this study conducts further investigations about the figure of Ki Hajar Dewantara and how its relevance in facing the challenges of the 21st century. Through deep understanding, we can adapt and integrate its concepts in modern education to create a more adaptive, inclusive, and holistic system.

THEORETICAL REVIEW

The 21st century, known as the era of digitalization, brings a number of new challenges in the world of education. The teaching and learning process that used to be centered on face-to-face interaction, is now starting to shift with the existence of digital learning methods. Technology, which facilitates access to information and communication, also brings its own challenges in terms of

information quality, integrity, and relevance. In this context, how can the principles of Ki Hajar Dewantara be adopted to ensure quality education is still realized?

Character education is one aspect that gets special attention in this century. In the midst of such a heavy flow of information, there are concerns about how education can shape the character of students who are strong, integrity, and responsible. Ki Hajar Dewantara always emphasizes the importance of emotional, spiritual, and intellectual education. How can this holistic approach be implemented in today's digital age? Other issues such as inclusivity, gender equality, and sustainability are also significant challenges in 21st century education. As a thinker who places education as a tool to advance the nation and society, Ki Hajar Dewantara's thoughts can provide valuable insights into how education can be a solution to these issues. In particular, how education can be used as an instrument to build a more inclusive, equitable, and sustainable society.

METHODOLOGY

In this study, a literature review was used for content analysis. The secondary data source of this study comes from a book written by Ki Hajar Dewantara, the main data source comes from writings, other works, or previous research on it. Library research methods are used to collect data. The inductive method, which answers the latest problems, is used to analyze the collected data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Biografi Ki Hajar Dewantara

With the name Raden Mas Suwardi Suryaningrat, Ki Hajar Dewantara, a philosophy of education, was born May 2, 1889. KHD is a descendant of the royal family who lived in Pakualaman temple in Yogyakarta. His mother was Raden Ayu Sandiyah, and his father was K.P.H. Suryaningrat. Nyai Ageng Serang is the ancestor of Sunan Kalijaga. At the age of 39, Raden Mas Suwardi Suryaningrat changed his name to Ki Hadjar Dewantara from Cucu Sri Paku Alam III. The artistic, cultural, and religious values of Ki Hajar Dewantara are strongly influenced by his environment since childhood. KHD was able to get along with the general public after changing its name. So the people at that time were more receptive to his struggle. On November 4, 1907, R.M. Soewardi Soeryaningrat and RA. Soetartinah married. They are the grandchildren of Sri Paku Alam III. Their marriage was officiated modestly at the end of August 1913 at Puri Suryaningratan Yogyakarta a few days before they left for exile in the Netherlands.

Ki Hadjar Dewantara died on April 26, 1959 at his home in Mujamuju, Yogyakarta. On April 29, his body was taken to Taman Siswa pavilion and then handed over to Taman Siswa Sublime Council. From the pavilion, the body was taken to Wijaya Brata Yogyakarta. Colonel Suharto, Commander of Diponegoro Military Command, was responsible for the funeral of Ki Hadjar Dewantara. Ki Hadjar Dewantara was named a "National Hero" on 28 November 1959. In connection with the date of birth of Ki Hadjar Dewantara, on December 16, 1959, the government designated May 2 as "National Education Day". Ki Hadjar Dewantara is bold, creative, dynamic, honest, simple, and consequential. He was a respected and respected national figure by both his supporters and opponents. He had a broad outlook and would continue to fight for his nation until the end of his life. Pure spirit, devotion, and sacrifice underlie his struggle to gain the independence of his country. Ki Hajar Dewantara not only studied at Paku Alam Palace, but also studied religion at the Kalasan pesantren under the guidance of KH. Abdurahman. After that, he received a formal education, which included:

1. ELS, Dutch elementary school III.
2. Kweek School, a teacher's school in Yogyakarta.
3. STOVIA Medical School located in Jakarta is STOVIA. KHD was unable to complete this course because Ki Hadjar Dewantara was ill for four months.

Written By Ki Hajar Dewantara

Many of Ki Hajar Dewantara's works were written because of his concern for education and culture. To this day, these works continue to be used as references in educational and cultural research.

1. The first book on education deals with the concept of education specifically. It is believed that national education is beneficial for human independence, unity, and people's lives. (Dewantara, 1977).
2. Culture is discussed in the second book. Articles on culture and art are included in this book. Culture is another term for culture, which means the result of human civilization or efforts to improve human life. Every culture or culture has many characteristics, but everything runs smoothly because everything is civilized (Dewantara, 1967).
3. The third book, which deals with politics and society, contains writings about youth and its struggles and the politics that shocked the Dutch imperialist world from 1913 to 1922.
4. The Author's Story and Life Struggle: In the fourth book of Ki Hajar Dewantara, the author who became a pioneer and independence hero discusses their life stories and struggles. (Utami, 2017).

Ki Hajar Dewantara's Concepts and Thoughts About Education

1. Tri Education Center:

- Family Education: Considered as the first and foremost center of education. Children first learn the principles of life in their family.
 - School Education: A place where formal knowledge is taught to students. The school also serves as a place to build character.
 - Community Education: Ki Hajar Dewantara views society as an educational environment that provides lessons about social life, cooperation, and interaction between individuals.
2. Ing Ngarso Sung Tulodo, Ing Madyo Mangun Karso, Tut Wuri Handayani. Ing Ngarso Sung Tulodo: Artinya, guru harus menjadi contoh bagi siswanya.
 - Ing Madyo Mangun Karso: Educators must be able to motivate students.
 - Tut Wuri Handayani: Educators must provide support from behind, be an encouragement for their students to keep going.
 3. Education Rooted in National Culture: Ki Hajar Dewantara emphasizes the importance of education based on national culture, so that students not only gain knowledge but also understand and appreciate the culture and values of their nation.
 4. Holistic Education: education should not only focus on the intellectual aspects of students, but also emotional, spiritual, and physical. An individual must be educated thoroughly to become a balanced person.
 5. Independence in Education: Ki Hajar Dewantara emphasizes the importance of independence in education. Educational institutions must have autonomy in decision-making and be free from external intervention, especially from colonial parties.
 6. Education as Empowerment: education is supposed to empower students, enable them to develop, understand their rights, and contribute positively to society and the nation.
 7. Education for All: Ki Hajar Dewantara argues that education should be accessible to all walks of life, no matter their social or economic status.

The Relevance of Ki Hajar Dewantara Thought in the Challenges of 21st Century Education

Ki Hajar Dewantara's thoughts on education, which originated in the early 20th century, remain of strong relevance in facing the challenges of education in the 21st century. In this era of fast-paced globalization and digitalization, the basic principles proposed by Ki Hajar Dewantara are becoming increasingly important. The relevance of Ki Hajar Dewantara's ideas in the challenges of 21st century education is as follows:

1. Holistic Education and Mental Wellbeing:

In an era where stress, anxiety, and other mental well-being issues are on the rise among the younger generation, the holistic education proposed by Ki Hajar Dewantara is becoming increasingly relevant. Education should not only

focus on academic progress but also on the emotional, physical, and spiritual development of students. This concept supports the needs of character education and the formation of a whole personality, providing students with the necessary skills and resilience to face the stresses of life in the 21st century.

2. Education Rooted in National Culture in the Era of Globalization:

In the midst of globalization that brings diverse cultures and ideas to every corner of the world, Ki Hajar Dewantara's thoughts on the importance of education rooted in national culture are becoming increasingly important. A deep understanding of national cultural identity and heritage helps students to interact with the world with greater confidence and understanding.

3. Education as Empowerment in the Age of Technology:

Technology has changed the way we learn, communicate, and work. In such a situation, Ki Hajar Dewantara's thoughts on education as a tool of empowerment become increasingly relevant. Education is supposed to arm students with the critical skills, problem-solving, and adaptability necessary in an ever-changing world.

4. Inclusive Education and Affordability:

Although technology has opened up access to information sources previously unavailable to many, educational gaps still exist. Ki Hajar Dewantara's ideas about education that should be available to all walks of life remind us of the importance of inclusive education and affordability.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

A well-known education figure in Indonesia, Ki Hajar Dewantara, is considered the founder of the national education system. Taman Siswa, founded by Raden Mas Soewardi Soerjaningrat, is an educational institution that emphasizes the importance of curriculum based on Indonesian culture and local principles. Education in Indonesia is based on his ideas that emphasize education based on national culture, independence, and holistic education. Besides being honored as the Father of National Education, Ki Hajar Dewantara has a legacy that continues to be maintained and celebrated to this day.

Ki Hajar Dewantara's views on education are still relevant when we face educational problems in the 21st century. In the era of globalization and digitalization, his principles of holistic education, self-reliance, and education rooted in national culture are becoming increasingly important. In the context of modern education that faces technological pressures, access gaps, and rapid changes in job demands, Ki Hajar Dewantara's approach that emphasizes character building, skills, adaptation, and self-understanding is becoming increasingly essential. So it can be known that even though it originated in the

early 20th century, the thought of Ki Hajar Dewantara remains a valuable guide in responding to contemporary education and preparing future generations who are complete and empowered.

REFERENCES

- Andini, T. R. & Pradana, M. (2022). *Character Education in the Digital Age: Reflections on the Thoughts of Ki Hajar Dewantara*. Semarang: Rasamala Press.
- Prasetyo, B. & Hartanto, W. (2019). *Ki Hajar Dewantara and Digital Education: An Analysis*. Surabaya: Gramedia Pustaka.
- Prasetyo, B., & Jumadi. (2018). The Relevance of Ki Hajar Dewantara Thought in the Industrial Revolution 4.0 Era. *Journal of Education: Theory, Research, and Development*.
- Purnama, S. & Dhani, A. (2022). *Ki Hajar Dewantara Thought Integration in the 21st Century Curriculum*. Jakarta: Erlangs.
- Rahardjo, M. (2017). *Ki Hajar Dewantara and National Character Education*. Jakarta: Kompas Media Nusantara.
- Rahmawati, I. N. & Sutanto, A. (2020). *Holistic Education in the Digital Age: Exploring the Philosophy of Ki Hajar Dewantara*. Jakarta: Bumi Aksara.
- Ratih, W. & Nugraha, D. (2023). *Ki Hajar Dewantara and Education's Response to Global Issues*. Solo: Andi Publisher.
- Son, I.N.D. (2019). Ki Hajar Dewantara's Thoughts in the Context of 21st Century Education. *Journal of Education and Culture*.
- Sutrisno, L. & Aditya, P. (2018). *Ki Hajar Dewantara in the World of Modern Education*. Bandung: Refika Aditama.
- Wijaya, A. & Utami, R. (2021). *Facing the 21st Century with the Philosophy of Ki Hajar Dewantara*. Yogyakarta: Student Library.